

Supplementary file: Search Strategy

PubMed

(pulmonary tuberculosis[MeSH Terms] OR tuberculosis, pulmonary[Title/Abstract] OR TB[Title/Abstract])

AND

(nursing care[MeSH Terms] OR nursing intervention[Title/Abstract] OR nursing[Title/Abstract])

AND

(adherence[MeSH Terms] OR compliance[Title/Abstract] OR knowledge[Title/Abstract] OR adverse events[Title/Abstract] OR sputum conversion[Title/Abstract] OR psychological function[Title/Abstract] OR satisfaction[Title/Abstract] OR self-efficacy[Title/Abstract] OR social function[Title/Abstract] OR anxiety scale[Title/Abstract] OR self-rating depression scale[Title/Abstract])